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What Are Answer Strategies Being Researched to Cure or Treat Cancer? Alireza Heidari^{1,2,3,4*}, Elena Locci^{1,2,3} and Silvia Raymond^{1,2,3}

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Abstract

Breast cancer radiotherapy is used for patients at high risk in areas such as family history of heart disease and the use of chemotherapy drugs. Imaging and treatment are performed. Because the most sensitive part of the patient's heart is located in the field of breast radiation therapy, radiation therapy is likely to cause heart complications for the patient. For patients at high risk of heart disease, deep tail radiation therapy is performed and thus the least radiation hits the heart tissue. And the side effects of treatment are greatly reduced. The technique of IMRT or "variable intensity radiation therapy" is another unique new method of radiation therapy.

Keywords: Cancer; Cells; Tissues; Tumors; Prevention; Prognosis; Diagnosis; Imaging; Screening; Treatment; Management

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Introduction

Breast cancers present with non-specific symptoms, such as bloating, office, gastrointestinal, abdominal pain, pelvic pain, or, in more advanced stages, as the mass becomes larger. What we need to emphasize more is that this cancer has non-specific symptoms and the person may not even realize that these symptoms are related to breast cancer. In the face of these symptoms, people

refer to various doctors, especially internal medicine and gastroenterologists, and after examinations, they find out that the mass was in the breast. This means that breast cancer mortality is higher than other genital cancers. Breast cancer has different categories, the most common of which is epithelial cancer. The reason for naming this group of cancers was that not all of them are the same in terms of prognosis; therefore, there are differences that vary in age and prognosis. The cancer may also present as acute symptoms such as intestinal obstruction, nausea and vomiting,

lung involvement and shortness of breath, and vague pain, or it may occur as Coincidence of an ultrasound performed for another reason can detect a lump in the breast, which is usually a sign of breast cancer, and patients should seek treatment. It is beneficial because it does not reduce mortality and leads us to use aggressive methods. We only screen people who are at high risk. Screening is not available in the general population and is only done in people at high risk. In other people in the community who have a moderate risk of cancer, screening is not done and we should only look at common symptoms that are completely nonspecific. There is another breast tumor that develops in the second or third decade of life in young girls and women, which is a group of breast germ cell tumors that usually appear early and the person feels a big belly, pelvic pain, pelvic pressure or symptoms. Acute should see a doctor. To diagnose it, a person undergoes an examination and ultrasound by a doctor to diagnose a breast mass and undergo surgery, and then to be diagnosed with breast cancer. Young women with this type of breast tumor usually have a good prognosis and it is true that they have treatments such as chemotherapy, but usually with a good prognosis they can live for many years and have many children; Therefore, we are happy if we encounter this tumor compared to the epithelial tumor, because this tumor occurs in old age and its average prevalence is 63 years, and people see a doctor at a higher stage. The mainstay of treatment for breast cancer is surgery and other treatments. Like chemotherapy, it can be a good help and may be done before or after surgery, depending on the patient's condition. Most breast tumors are benign, and based on the characteristics given to us by ultrasound, surgery is performed for this group of patients in cases where we suspect. It is better to perform this surgery in centers that can report the type of tumor pathology to the surgeon during the surgery, so that if there is malignancy, the surgeon can perform the operation completely and determine the stage of the tumor and cancer in

the same surgery. Do not have reoperation, which lumps should be operated on and which lumps do not need surgery, which is diagnosed by gynecologists and oncologists [1-490].

Results and Discussion

Breast cancer is the most common cancer among women and accounts for 25% of all cancers among women. The World Health Organization says that in 2020 alone, more than 2.3 million new cases of breast cancer were identified worldwide. This is while 685 thousand people die every year due to this cancer. Therefore, experts always emphasize that women should have their breasts examined regularly for signs of cancer. One in eight women will develop some degree of breast cancer in their lifetime. Although cancer is more likely to occur in all age groups, it is usually more likely to occur after the age of 50. The most common symptom of breast cancer is a lump on the breast. However, there are other key signs in this regard. Women may also suffer from chest pain as blood comes out of the nipple. The skin around the breasts may also be sunken or bulging, or the person may complain of other skin changes. The American Cancer Center has identified nipple sagging as a common symptom of breast cancer in women. However, because breast cancer has many different types, the symptoms associated with it can also manifest themselves differently. However, not every breast change means breast cancer, and it should not scare women. The UK Public Health Service says the cause of breast cancer in women is still unknown, but some factors play a role. For example, if your close relatives have breast or ovarian cancer, your risk of developing this cancer increases significantly. Like many other cancers, having a healthy, balanced diet with regular activity and exercise reduces the risk of breast cancer. Research has shown that breastfeeding women not only promotes proper nutrition and health of the baby, but also significantly reduces the risk of breast cancer in these women.

Conclusion

Despite medical advances, cancer treatment is still limited and difficult. However, studies have shown that a lack of a vitamin can provide clues to the progression of the disease. A number of lifestyle factors are involved in causing cancer; while poor diet is one of the main culprits, evidence suggests that deficiencies in vital vitamins and minerals can also cause DNA damage. Although most vitamins are absorbed through the diet, some of them, especially vitamin D, are obtained through exposure to sunlight. Studies have shown that vitamin D can protect against cancer because of its effect on cell life cycle. Vitamin D levels were measured in all women with cancer after diagnosis. Serum levels of at least 30 ng / ml were sufficiently determined. None of the participants took vitamin D supplements at the beginning of the study. Researchers report high levels of vitamin D deficiency in women with breast cancer. The results showed that 55.6% of breast cancer patients suffer from vitamin D deficiency, while 49.3% of the control group and 26.2% of cancer patients suffer from vitamin D deficiency compared to the healthy control group. They take. The researchers found that an insufficient concentration or deficiency of vitamin D was diagnosed in 81.8% of women with cancer and 69.6% of women without cancer. These findings are consistent with previous studies showing a higher rate of vitamin D deficiency in women with breast cancer. The active form of vitamin D and its derivatives may have antitumor effects by negatively regulating growth factor signaling, in addition to its effects on proliferation, differentiation, and angiogenesis. Machado added that the effects of the active vitamin D metabolite on the breast are mediated by vitamin D receptors, which regulate genes that regulate cell proliferation and differentiation. This vitamin may reduce the risk of cancer by preventing cell proliferation and differentiation, and prevents angiogenesis in

both healthy and malignant breasts. Several uncontrolled studies have shown a higher rate of vitamin D deficiency in women with breast cancer. This study adds to growing research showing an inverse association between vitamin D deficiency and the incidence of many types of cancer, including cancers of the colon, kidney, lung and pancreas. Previous studies have shown that vitamin D supplementation can reduce the risk of cancer by up to 38%. It was previously believed that this vitamin could only reduce the risk of dying from cancer. Vitamin D deficiency affects one billion people worldwide, with symptoms including depression, bone and back pain, and fatigue.

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